

MODERN THEORIES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME

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Today, polycystic ovary syndrome is considered by specialists as a heterogeneous disease. From 10% to 20% of women of reproductive age are diagnosed with this disease. In addition to affecting the reproductive system, polycystic ovary syndrome is accompanied by changes in endocrine organs, the cardiovascular system, and can be the cause of metabolic disorders. Pathogenetic theories of development are updated annually with new data, and at the current level the syndrome is considered as a genetically inherited predisposition. Our literature search showed that there is a clear correlation between polycystic ovary syndrome and polymorphism of some genes.

Keywords: polycystic ovary syndrome, gene polymorphism, VEGF gene

Introduction. Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a complex multifactorial disease with an unexplained etiology [1,2]. Some researchers point to hormonal changes and a change in the ratio between FSH/LH, an increase in the level of androgens, which leads to disturbances in the menstrual cycle with oligomenorrhea or amenorrhea. An increase in the level of testosterone in the blood plasma is the reason for the increase in the conversion of the latter in adipose tissue to estrone with subsequent conversion to estradiol, which disrupts the ratio between LH and FG hormones and disrupts ovulation. Against the background of impaired fat metabolism, the role of adiponectin and leptin has recently been considered, and a violation of their ratio is considered a risk factor for insulin resistance with the whole complex of subsequent changes. In recent years, many studies point to insulin resistance in the development of PCOS. In women with increased BMI, metabolic syndrome, obesity and detected hyperinsulinemia in blood serum, there is a connection with PCOS [2,3].

The study of biochemical and pathogenetic mechanisms of the development of PCOS in patients who are related by family ties of the first line led scientists to believe that PCOS has a genetic nature. This pattern is observed in 20-40% of cases of disease manifestation, which is confirmed by identical manifestations of PCOS in twins. The contribution of genetic factors to the development of PCOS is 79%, and other exo and endogenous factors, such as: weight, age, metabolic disorders have a significant modifying effect on the clinical manifestations of PCOS. Specialists continue to search for genes that regulate hypothalamic-pituitary interactions, are responsible for steroidogenesis in the ovaries, are genetic factors of insulin resistance, and regulate carbohydrate metabolism, the appearance and development of oxidative stress [1,4].

PCOS is considered a heterogeneous disease and one of the factors of its development may be a violation of ovarian angiogenesis, which is associated with the modification of the vascular endothelial growth factor

VEGF. The VEGF gene belongs to the PDGF/VEGF growth factor family and is located on site 6p21.1 and contains 9 exons. This gene is expressed in theca cells and is involved in the physiological regulation of ovarian angiogenesis. Polymorphisms are noted in the promoter and intronic regions and may be the cause of PCOS. The insufficiently elucidated etiology of PCOS and the possible connection with polymorphisms rs2010963 and rs833061 of the VEGF gene to the development of polycystic ovary syndrome determines the relevance of our research [2,5].

The purpose of our study was to conduct a literature search regarding the current views on the factors of the development of polycystic ovary syndrome.

Research materials and methods. Summarize and analyze scientific publications over the past 5 years on the topic of this study. Databases and search engines were used to search for literary sources: Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed by keywords on the research topic.

Main part. Biochemical and pathophysiological mechanisms of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). According to modern data, polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) occurs in 8-10% of women of reproductive age. This is a pathology of the reproductive system, which is manifested by changes in the endocrine organs, the cardiovascular system and causes metabolic disorders. Changes in the ovaries are symptomatically manifested by disorders of the menstrual cycle such as oligo or amenorrhea, the appearance of cysts and, as a result, the development of infertility. Regulation of the release of hormones by the ovaries is regulated by complex neuro-humoral interactions [6]. This process begins with the release of gonadotropic releasing factors by neurons of the hypothalamus, which, based on the principle of negative feedback, cause the production of gonadotropic hormones in a cyclical manner. Follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) is responsible for the growth and maturation of follicles, and luteinizing hormone (LH), which, along with oxytocin, is responsible for ovulation [7]. Under the influence of FSH and LH,

appropriate changes occur in the ovaries. A maturing follicle is a source of estrogens, the level of which increases from day 1 to day 14 of the 28th menstrual cycle. According to the principle of feedback, estrogens through the hypothalamic-pituitary link stimulate the production of LH, ovulation and the formation of the corpus luteum, which is a source of progesterone. Progesterone is responsible for changes in the endometrium of the uterus, namely the processes of proliferation and secretion. The walls of the maturing follicle are a source of both estrogens and androgens. In women with PCOS, excessive production of LH is associated with impaired follicle formation and greater sensitivity of the receptor of theca cells to LH, which is accompanied by hyperandrogenism [8]. An increase in the level of the enzyme epoxyhydrolase 1, which plays a role in steroidogenesis and breaks down aromatic compounds, causes excessive production of androgens, which slows down the transformation of testosterone into estradiol in women of reproductive age and is associated with the development of PCOS. Cyclic changes in the ovary are associated with the production of estrogens by the cells of the maturing follicle in the first phase of the menstrual cycle, and progesterone in the luteinizing phase by the corpus luteum, which is formed at the site of the ruptured follicle [9]. Hyperandrogenism disrupts the interaction of progesterone with its receptors in the hypothalamus, by modulating gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptors, thereby reducing the sensitivity of specialized neurons to progesterone, which increases the shift between FSH and LH. In addition to anovulatory cycles, hyperandrogenism can be manifested by excessive body hair, thinning hair on the head, the appearance of acne, obesity and the development of concomitant pathology: diabetes, hypertension, cholesterol metabolism disorders, diseases of the cardiovascular system, hyperplasia of the adrenal glands, changes in the endometrium. Today, experts assume that up to 70% of women with this problem do not even seek help. This disease can debut with metabolic disorders, such as diabetes, obesity, or the onset of hypertension. The mechanism of PCOS development is heterogeneous and a classification was formed back in 1990, which took into account many subcategories of the manifestation of this disease. A prerequisite is the presence of the Rotterdam criteria associated with hyperandrogenism and anovulatory cycles, which made it possible to identify certain phenotypes of PCOS pathology. Type A includes all three criteria: chronic oligo/amenorrhea, ultrasound signs of PCOS, and laboratory-confirmed hyperandrogenism. Type B combines hyperandrogenism and chronic anovulation, type C - hyperandrogenism and ultrasound signs and D - chronic anovulation and ultrasound signs. In some studies, data were given on the peculiarities of the distribution of different phenotypes depending on the country, race, and there is even a difference in the clinical presentations of patients with PCOS.

The considered biochemical mechanisms of PCOS development indicate insulin resistance in women with PCOS. It is insulin that is responsible for steroidogenesis in the theca cells of the ovaries and, to-

gether with insulin-like growth factor and LH, enhances the expression of CYP450c17 mRNA and triggers excessive production of androgens [10]. Hyperinsulinemia blocks the liver's production of a protein that normally binds insulin-like growth factor and thereby regulates the level of free testosterone in the blood. Increased activity of insulin-like growth factor inhibits folliculogenesis by activating apoptosis of granulosa cells. It is symptomatically manifested by anovulatory bleeding and the accumulation of immature follicles. Hyperinsulinemia causes metabolic disorders that lead to the development of obesity and the development of diabetes. In recent years, inositol and its isomers: myo-inositol and chiro-inositol have been considered in the pathogenesis of these changes. For normal functioning, it is necessary to convert myo-inositol into chiro-inositol, which is inhibited under conditions of increased insulin levels. The accumulation of myo-inositol increases the sensitivity of ovarian tissue to insulin, which distorts the functioning of the ovaries and their sensitivity to FS and worsens the quality of oocytes [11]. Another important effect of insulin on adipose tissue is the stimulation of lipogenesis and inhibition of lipolysis, which is an additional factor in the development of obesity and metabolic syndrome. Hyperandrogenism is a factor that causes the development of inflammation due to increased peroxidation processes under the influence of interleukins: IL-6, IL-1. IL-1, IL-1 β . IL-1 blocks receptors for FSH and LH. This theory is supported by a decrease in the level of amino acids in the blood plasma against the background of an increase in C-reactive protein. Insulin resistance, which contributes to the modification of GLUT 4 receptors and leads to an increase in the level of glucose against the background of hyperandrogenism, increases oxidative stress. Strengthening of the mechanisms of molecular cell adhesion and growth of tumor necrosis factor (TNF- α) in blood plasma indicates the activation of the autoimmune mechanism of PCOS and increased hyperandrogenism. TNF- α increases insulin resistance and stimulates theca cell proliferation. Under these conditions, dehydroepiandrosterone reduces the level of interferon γ and disrupts the physiological functioning of the ovaries, which manifests itself in inhibition of growth, maturation of follicles and ovulation. Against the background of disruption of cyclicity in the release of estrogens and progesterone, TNF- α and IL-1 β contribute to the development of ovarian fibrosis [12].

The development of oxidative stress is accompanied by the release of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (O $_2^-$, H $_2$ O $_2$ and OH $^-$) and a decrease in the activity of antioxidant enzymes. The increase in oxidation processes causes the formation of ROS with nitric oxide and releases highly reactive peroxynitrite, which inhibits the activity of superoxide dismutase, which models steroidogenesis and affects the neurons of the lateral hypothalamus, which regulate eating behavior and are responsible for the development of hypothalamic obesity. Increased formation of ROS is considered as one of the factors of obesity in connection with the possible effect of ROS on the proliferation of adipocytes and increased formation of preadipocytes.

An increase in the level of testosterone in the blood plasma is the reason for the increase in the conversion of the latter in adipose tissue to estrone with subsequent conversion to estradiol, which disrupts the ratio between LH and FG hormones and disrupts ovulation. Against the background of impaired fat metabolism, the role of adiponectin and leptin has recently been considered, and a violation of their ratio is considered a risk factor for insulin resistance with the whole complex of subsequent changes. Obesity is accompanied by the accumulation of adipocytes in visceral fat, which causes hypoxia and increases oxidative stress, and also becomes a factor in insulin resistance and hyperglycemia, under conditions of which hyperinsulinemia increases [13]. This was confirmed in the works of American researchers, who established the similarity between the adipose tissue of women with PCOS and that of men. The specified changes in adipose tissue, insulin resistance can be the beginning of the development of PCOS. Accumulation of visceral fat affects the expression of 11 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase, an enzyme important in the conversion of cortisone to active cortisol. Enzymes, 17 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenases, which catalyze the transition of androstenedione to testosterone, testosterone to dihydrotestosterone, and estrone to estradiol are expressed in adipose tissue. High levels of leptin are associated with increased insulin resistance and increased testosterone production. Leptin inhibits the conversion of androgens to estrogens by inhibiting aromatase mRNA expression in ovarian cells. Adiponectin affects LH secretion in the pituitary gland. The research was carried out by the Department of Gynecology and Perinatology of the National University of Health Care of Ukraine named after PL Shupyk established that the use of adiponectin normalizes the level of leptin and restores the effects of insulin on insulin-dependent cells, normalizes metabolic changes and opens perspectives for the use of this drug in the prevention of PCOS. There is no doubt that the genetic cause of the action of insulin on the ovaries [14, 15].

At the current level, specialists consider the causes of PCOS as multifactorial, which is confirmed by biochemical, molecular studies and genetic examinations.

Genetic theory of polycystic ovary syndrome development. The study of biochemical and pathogenetic mechanisms of the development of PCOS in patients who are related by family ties of the first line led scientists to believe that PCOS has a genetic nature [16]. This pattern is observed in 20-40% of cases of disease manifestation, which is confirmed by identical manifestations of PCOS in twins. The contribution of genetic factors to the development of PCOS is 79%, and other exo and endogenous factors, such as: weight, age, metabolic disorders have a significant modifying effect on the clinical manifestations of PCOS [17]. Specialists continue to search for genes that regulate hypothalamic-pituitary interactions, are responsible for steroidogenesis in the ovaries, are genetic factors of insulin resistance, and regulate carbohydrate metabolism, the appearance and development of oxidative stress [18]. The existence of six genetic loci associated with

PCOS, which regulate the pituitary release of gonadotropic hormones, has been proven, and using the method of Mendelian randomization, it is possible to assert the connection of PCOS with a high body mass index (BMI), insulin resistance, and a low concentration of globulins, which "active sex hormones [19,20]. Experts confirmed the connection between the alleles responsible for the later onset of menopause and the risk of PCOS. Increased levels of LH have been proven in women with PCOS. Changes in LH regulation depend on modifications of the gene that encodes the β -subunit of LH. Studies conducted by Furui and others proved the presence of double-point mutations Trp 8 Arg and Ile 15 Thr and single-point missense mutation Gln 102 Ser in the β -subunit of LH. These mutations are manifestations of polymorphisms that increase the level of LH. The FSH receptor is encoded by a gene that consists of 14 exons and is located on chromosome 2p16.3. The mutation of the gene distorts the effects of FSH on the receptors, which is manifested by impaired maturation and growth of follicles, which leads to the development of PCOS [21,22].

Biochemical methods have established that the process of aromatization of androgens to estrogens depends on P450-aromatase. This process of complex biochemical transformations, which begins with the transformation of cholesterol into progesterone. P450c17 α catalyzes the chain of transformations of 17-hydroxyprogesterone from pregnenellone and 17 OH-progesterone from progesterone with further transformation into dehydroepiandrosterone and androstenedione. Polymorphism of the genes responsible for the synthesis of the enzyme and cytochrome P 450 complex is considered a factor in the pathogenesis of PCOS, for example, the CYP11A1 gene encodes P450scc enzymes. CYP11a encodes the conversion of cholesterol to progesterone. The enzyme encoded by this gene is located on the inner membrane of mitochondria, and the gene is located on the 15q24.1 site and contains 10 exons [23]. Increased activity of CYP11A causes hyperandrogenism. Research conducted in South India established the presence of 15 allelic variations of the CYP11 A gene and the most common 8 alleles. This study clearly emphasizes that the recurrence of these 8 alleles correlates with a 3-fold increase in PCOS. Similar data were obtained in China regarding the role of the CYP11 A gene. The CYP17 gene regulates P450c17 α . The gene consists of 8 exons and is located on chromosome 10q24.32. If a single nucleotide polymorphism is observed in the promoter region of the gene, the risk of PCOS increases. The CYP19 gene encodes aromatase P450 arom [24]. P450 arom is a member of the gene superfamily. Biochemical studies have established that aromatase consists of 410 amino acid residues and catalyzes various reactions in its active center. These 3 reactions take place on substrates: androstenedione, testosterone, and 16 α -hydroxytestosterone, which in the aromatization reaction by adding oxygen form the phenolic ring of estrogens and turn into estrone, 17 β -estradiol, and 17 β , 16 α -estriol [25,26].

Cytochrome P450 aromatase is located in the endoplasmic reticulum and is responsible for the synthesis of estrogens. In all women with PCOS, the amount of estradiol P450 aroma-mRNA in the follicles decreased and aromatase activity decreased accordingly, which may be the reason for the accumulation of androgens and impaired follicle formation. Studies of the role of CYP17A1 gene polymorphisms are described ambiguously in the literature: scientific works describe both an increase in the frequency of CYP17A1 alleles and genotypes in PCOS, as well as the absence of a connection with the disease [27,28]. The genetic determination of the 5-alpha-reductase enzyme in the development of PCOS has also been proven. Described clinical studies of 237 women with PCOS who underwent biochemical measurements of 5-alpha-reductase and conducted genetic studies that established a connection between SRD5A1 and SRD5A2 gene polymorphisms and clinical manifestations. Androgen receptor genes consider the reduction of CAG repeats in the exon of this gene as a factor in hyperandrogenism. Insulin resistance is a leading factor in the development of PCOS, the gene encoding insulin receptors INSR has a polymorphism in exon 17-21, a polymorphism of tyrosine kinase, which is associated with the development of insulin resistance. The CYP21 gene encodes 21-hydroxylase and is responsible for the biochemical transformation of 7-hydroxyprogesterone into 11-deoxycortisol. This gene consists of 10 exons and is located on the site 6p21.33. Deficiency of the 21-hydroxylase enzyme is a consequence of an autosomal recessive mutation of this gene and an increase in 17-hydroxyprogesterone in the serum of women [29,30]. The sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG) gene binds to androgens and transports them to their site of action, thus regulating hormone levels. The gene for this hormone is located on chromosome 17p13-p12. The transcriptional activity of the gene is regulated by the pentanucleotide polymorphism (TAAAA)_n in the promoter region. Greek scientists conducted research and established a link between the repetition of the pentanucleotide, which causes a low level of SHBG in the blood serum, which promotes the effect of testosterone on target cells. The AMG gene, which is associated with female fertility, consists of 5 exons and is located on chromosome 19q13.3. Polymorphism of this gene changes the fertility of women and there is evidence of its involvement in the development of PCOS [31,32].

The insulin gene INS via Pk-B (protein kinase-B) is found in the theca cells of women with PCOS. The regulatory site of the INS gene is embedded in the VNTR and has a polymorphism. However, the involvement of this gene polymorphism in the development of PCOS is controversial.

The gene that encodes insulin receptors (INSR) consists of two subunits and is located on the 19th chromosome. Studies conducted on women with PCOS and obesity have not established correlations between gene polymorphisms and the syndrome.

The relationship between polymorphisms rs2010963 and rs833061 of the VEGF gene and changes in a woman's hormonal profile. PCOS is considered a heterogeneous disease and one of the factors

of its development may be a violation of ovarian angiogenesis, which is associated with the modification of the vascular endothelial growth factor VEGF. Research conducted at the Lviv National Medical University established reliable links between the rs2010963 polymorphism and the development of diabetic retinopathy, which proves the involvement of the gene in the regulation of blood vessel growth.

The VEGF gene belongs to the PDGF/VEGF growth factor family and is located on site 6p21.1 and contains 9 exons. This gene is expressed in theca cells and is involved in the physiological regulation of ovarian angiogenesis. Polymorphisms are noted in the promoter and intronic regions and may be the cause of PCOS.

The VEGF rs833061 T and rs2010963 G alleles correlate with increased VEGF levels and the development of PCOS. Studies by Chinese scientists note that the rs833061 polymorphism of the VEGF gene correlates with the risk of PCOS. The influence of gene polymorphisms on the risk of PCOS was reported in the literature, but this analysis was not conducted among Ukrainian women [15,33].

Conclusion. Our review of the literature established the polygenicity of factors in the development of PCOS and genetic factors play a leading role in the development of this disease. It is promising to study the genetic theory regarding the predisposition to the development of PCOS, which will open a new direction in the search for effective drugs that contribute to the reparation of certain areas of the pathological process.

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